
BRIEFING¹

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Nature+Energy: Contributions to Ireland's draft National Restoration Plan

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Background

The [Nature+Energy project](#) worked with Wind Energy Ireland and nine industry partners on nine windfarm study sites in Ireland to develop tools and approaches to enhance and restore biodiversity on windfarms. This included the development of nine site-specific biodiversity action plans and a set of biodiversity guidelines for the windfarm sector. The nine exemplar windfarm sites span eight counties (Galway, Wexford, Leitrim, Roscommon, Meath, Cork, Kilkenny and Donegal). During the course of the project, a policy analysis² was carried out to assess the alignment of site-specific and sectoral biodiversity actions with the relevant regional, national and international policy contexts. The regional-level policy documents analysed for each study site included the relevant County Development Plan, Local Authority Climate Action Plan and, where available, the county-level Biodiversity Action Plan. Awareness of such policy alignment has the potential to motivate industry to be 'ahead of the game' by implementing such biodiversity actions even if not yet legally required to do so.

Under the EU Nature Restoration Law³, Ireland is obliged to submit to the European Commission a draft National Restoration Plan (NRP) by 1 September 2026. The policy analysis carried out in the Nature+Energy (N+E) project provides useful insights for the drafting of Ireland's NRP. The heading and numbering of each paragraph below reflects the relevant section of the NRP template provided to Member States by the European Commission.

Insights from Nature+Energy that inform Ireland's draft National Restoration Plan

2.1.1 Overview of the national context (political, economic, environmental and social context)

The policy context outlined in the introduction to each of the nine site-specific BAPs highlights relevant national policies for biodiversity, including Ireland's 4th National Biodiversity Action Plan 2023-2030 and Climate Action and Low Carbon Development (Amendment) Act 2021. Arguably the regional contexts should be referenced in this overview as this will be the main implementation level. The introductions to the site-specific BAPs highlight where regional policy documents are relevant to biodiversity, notably

¹ Suggested citation: Brennan, R. (2025) *Briefing on the Nature+Energy project contributions to the drafting of Ireland's National Restoration Plan*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18336291>

² This analysis is included in a policy brief which identified policy gaps and synergies for the protection and enhancement of biodiversity on Ireland's windfarms. See Brennan, R., King, E., Stout, J.C., Buckley, Y.M., Donohue, I. (2026) *Policy Brief for Biodiversity Enhancement and Restoration on Onshore Windfarms in Ireland*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18316069>

³ Article 16, Regulation (EU) 2024/1991 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 June 2024 on nature restoration and amending Regulation (EU) 2022/869

County Development Plans, Local Authority Climate Action Plans and, where available, county-level Biodiversity Action Plans.

2.1.2 Overview of the governance and administrative structure defined for the implementation of the plan

The N+E policy analysis covers 8 different counties. It highlights which regional policies are likely to be more effective (action-based) in terms of biodiversity conservation, enhancement and restoration and which are more aspirational. This flags the need for particular attention to be paid to how NRP measures will be implemented in practice, as regional policy contexts differ in terms of effective and action-based nature restoration goals, aims, targets and policies. The N+E project's insights into regional policy differences highlight where there may be a need for more targeted action-based approaches in the regional policy context for the effective implementation of the NRP.

2.2.1 Preparation process and outcome of public participation and stakeholders' involvement

The policy and socio-cultural analysis for each of the nine exemplar windfarm sites highlights examples of existing local engagement in biodiversity-related initiatives such as biodiversity community engagement events or local biodiversity-related community groups. These provide helpful entry points and foundations for civil society to participate in the elaboration of the NRP. Similarly useful is the identification of the study-site counties that have appointed or intend to appoint Community Biodiversity Liaison Officers to support the development and delivery of biodiversity, education, conservation and restoration projects.

2.2.3 References and web links

The N+E policy analysis references the relevant policy documents such as Local Authority Climate Action Plans, County Development Plans and, where available, county-level Biodiversity Action Plans.

2.3.1 Considerations of the diversity of regional characteristics in regions, including their social, economic and cultural requirements

The N+E policy analysis references the relevant policy documents such as Local Authority Climate Action Plans, County Development Plans and, where available, county-level Biodiversity Action Plans. The analysis also references socio-cultural contexts that reflect the interconnections between nature and people through the richness of both natural and cultural heritage, including stories and place names that reflect traditions, language, and ecological knowledge that help preserve both cultural identity and environmental awareness, while deepening engagement and fostering a sense of shared stewardship. Understanding biodiversity and cultural heritage through local stories of lived experience and the etymology of place names is one way of creating space for a different starting point for conversations about the biodiversity, climate and pollution crises. As such, these examples from the N+E project can help to inspire an inclusive NRP that frames humans as participants in an interdependent web of life, rather than protectors or destroyers who are in charge of and control natural resources. They also have the creative capacity to open up locally rooted possibilities for worlds to emerge where humans and more-than-human species exist and flourish together, by bringing our attention to human-nature relationships of mutual care.

2.3.3 References and web links

The N+E policy analysis references the relevant policy documents such as Local Authority Climate Action Plans, County Development Plans and, where available, county-level Biodiversity Action Plans. The analysis also references regional examples of the interconnections between people and place.

4.1.1 Co-benefits for climate change mitigation; and

4.2.6 Other policies taken into account, where applicable

The N+E policy analysis identifies synergies between recommended biodiversity actions in the nine exemplar windfarm sites' biodiversity action plans and the relevant Local Authority Climate Action Plan. This provides regional-level examples of areas where climate change mitigation actions are already connected to biodiversity protection, enhancement and restoration.